

Research Article

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Understanding seismic hazard resilience in Montenegro: A qualitative analysis of community preparedness and response capabilities

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Abstract: Enhancing resilience against seismic hazards in earthquake-prone regions is essential for reducing the devastating impacts of disasters. Seismic resilience refers to a community's ability to withstand and recover from earthquake impacts, while preparedness gaps are the areas where current measures are insufficient to effectively respond to or mitigate earthquake damage. This study focuses on Montenegro – a region with frequent seismic activity – aiming to assess resilience levels, identify critical gaps in preparedness, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing response strategies. Using qualitative methods, including semi-structured interviews, the research gathered insights from residents of Montenegro's most vulnerable cities: Nikšić, Podgorica, Bar, Kotor, Cetinje, Budva, Herceg Novi, and Berane. Participants, chosen for their first-hand experience with significant earthquake impacts, provided valuable perspectives on various aspects of resilience, from local

government response to individual preparedness. This research revealed significant disparities in resilience across communities: for instance, approximately 62.5% of the respondents highlighted inadequate education as a barrier to effective earthquake preparedness, and only 37.5% reported awareness of basic earthquake response procedures. Furthermore, while some communities, such as urban areas with accessible services, reported higher preparedness levels, rural areas showed deficiencies, with 50% of the respondents from these areas identifying a lack of organized drills and limited public awareness initiatives. These findings underscore the urgent need for community-specific preparedness programs and enhancements in both structural resilience and public education to bolster community readiness effectively. Also, findings highlight the need for customized preparedness programs tailored to specific community needs, alongside improvements in structural safety measures and educational outreach. The study underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach involving detailed risk assessments, community-focused preparedness training, and stronger public awareness initiatives. Furthermore, the study calls for enhanced local government capabilities to sustain proactive response measures, including rapid mobilization of emergency resources and regular disaster simulations, to build long-term resilience across communities.

Keywords: disaster, seismic hazard, seismic resilience, Montenegro, qualitative analysis, local preparedness, response mechanisms, vulnerability assessment, public awareness

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1 Introduction

Global studies on seismic resilience provide valuable insights [1,2], particularly those conducted in regions with similar seismic profiles [3], such as coastal and mountainous areas where structural challenges and infrastructure needs closely parallel those in Montenegro. Local communities adopt a range of measures to prepare for seismic events, such as launching preparedness programs, offering counselling

services, and assessing the earthquake resilience of building groups [4]. Notable research from Indonesia highlights the vital role of community readiness, promoting the adoption of earthquake hazard maps and disaster readiness training to strengthen resilience [5,6]. Further studies in Bengkulu delve into how the residential environment impacts disaster preparedness, showing the influence of settlement conditions on community readiness for seismic events [7]. Research on the Italian Apennines also shows that historical exposure to seismic activity influences community perceptions of earthquake risk and preparedness. Overall, this research shows that the levels of concern and readiness vary significantly when looking at past experiences with heat stress and roles within the community [8]. These insights underscore the necessity of crafting preparedness strategies finely tuned to the local context and distinct community characteristics [3,5,9,10].

Seismic resilience forms a core pillar of disaster management, focusing on improving readiness and the ability to respond in earthquake-prone areas. Seismic resilience refers to a community's ability to withstand, respond to, and recover from an earthquake. It involves implementing preventive measures, designing infrastructure that can endure seismic forces, and having robust response systems in place to quickly restore normalcy after an event. This concept includes structural integrity, emergency preparedness, and adaptive capacity in the face of seismic hazards [11]. Research in this area highlights the necessity of assessing and enhancing resilience through diverse strategies [12,13]. For instance, an innovative assessment framework was unveiled in Taipei City, evaluating earthquake risks and resilience in the power infrastructure based on criteria like robustness, rapidity, redundancy, and resourcefulness [14]. In more remote areas, such as near the Dead Sea Fault in Israel, tailored self-assessment tools have been developed to foster deeper personal and family involvement in earthquake preparedness [15]. Moreover, research in Iran emphasizes the urgent need to boost seismic resilience at educational establishments, prioritizing retrofitting initiatives to enhance resilience indicators [16].

Montenegro's susceptibility to seismic activity has been underscored by historical events, notably the 1979 earthquake, which caused extensive structural damage and highlighted the region's vulnerabilities [17]. In Montenegro, seismic resilience is shaped by factors such as building age, type (e.g. high-rise structures, heritage sites), and regional exposure to seismic risks, with historical data revealing the frequency and the intensity of past events, notably in coastal and urban areas [18,19]. Also, multiple factors significantly influence the seismic resilience of structures. For high-rise buildings made of reinforced concrete along the Montenegrin coast, critical factors

include inter-storey drift (relative horizontal movement or displacement between two consecutive floors of a building during an earthquake), wall rotations, and shear capacity, which are keys in assessing their seismic performance [20]. The resilience of such buildings also hinges on the configuration of the structural system and the classification of the seismic zone [21]. Furthermore, the dynamic properties of these structures play an essential role in seismic design, as evidenced by comparisons with local and EC8 standards [22]. The structural integrity of heritage masonry buildings is undermined by poor craftsmanship and the absence of routine maintenance, heightening their risk during seismic events [19]. In regions with high seismic risk, such as Blida City, evaluations of building resilience often concentrate on vulnerability curves, states of damage, timelines for reconstruction, and related costs, all crucial for enhancing seismic resilience [23]. Examples from other countries, such as community-based disaster education programs in Italy and structural retrofitting efforts in Japan [1,24], provide adaptable frameworks that can be tailored to address Montenegro's specific challenges, including aging buildings, low public awareness, and varying institutional readiness.

The primary objectives of this study are to assess the current state of seismic resilience, identify critical gaps in local preparedness, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing response mechanisms. In this research, we carried out eight semi-structured interviews with individuals from regions highly prone to seismic activities, particularly those who have experienced notable earthquake impacts. In relation to this, the main aims of this research are to (i) discover the current panorama of seismic resilience; (ii) evaluate of critical points in local preparedness; and (iii) assess effectiveness of the existing response mechanisms. We interviewed eight people living in areas of the world with a high-risk national or regional seismic events, such as those experienced by others we had spoken to about earthquakes. Respondents were from several Montenegrin towns prone to earthquakes: Nikšić, Podgorica, Bar, Kotor, Cetinje, Budva, Herceg Novi, and Berane. To achieve greater comprehension and improved capacity to process estimates on community quake resilience, structured interviews were considered essential. These interviews materially extended the results, allowing us to flesh out the responses of the questionnaire into a more sophisticated examination of local resilience mechanisms. All participants were asked the same questions, so data were collected in a standardized way. However, despite that flexibility, it was still an interview and we tailored each at the moment based on how people were responding or what motivated them. This approach facilitated a rich discourse and enabled researchers to capture individual experiences as well as residents' various

responses towards community resilience. In addition to capturing rich qualitative data, the approach reinforced rigor in the research methodology by directly involving those living with the impact of seismic events. This research plays a vital role in tackling Montenegro's seismic challenges, shedding light on both the strengths and weaknesses of local communities in coping with earthquakes. By pinpointing key gaps in preparedness and evaluating existing response strategies, it offers valuable insights that can shape targeted approaches to boost seismic resilience across the region. This comprehensive methodology not only bolsters disaster mitigation efforts but also aims to enhance community preparedness and adaptability, ultimately contributing to a safer, more stable environment for Montenegro's earthquake-vulnerable areas.

1.1 Literature review

A thorough exploration of community resilience in earthquake scenarios, as found in scholarly literature, highlights various critical aspects. Researchers emphasize the crucial role of structural components – including buildings, hospitals, schools, and other infrastructure – in coping with the consequences of seismic disturbances [25]. Evaluating the resilience of buildings is deemed essential for the overall resilience of communities, with factors like repair costs, occupancy rates, and asset values being key indicators [26]. Such evaluations often rely on metrics that include repair timelines, cost-effectiveness of retrofitting efforts, and structural adaptability to seismic events [27]. Effective earthquake disaster management involves community participation to enhance adaptive behaviours, underscored by risk awareness, education, disaster mitigation, and collaborative efforts between residents, government agencies, and other stakeholders [28]. Community resilience is about overcoming shared challenges and trauma, relying on social networks, technological innovations, and strong infrastructural support [29]. Studies in this area often examine how communities use these resources to rapidly mobilize and maintain continuity during and after seismic events [30,31]. Assessing seismic resilience in groups of buildings involves scrutinizing potential hazards, appraising the performance of individual buildings, and collectively evaluating the resilience of these clusters by incorporating seismic hazard maps and vulnerability assessments to better inform structural resilience strategies [7].

Also, research into earthquake resilience covers a broad spectrum of topics, including structural design principles, community preparedness, the resilience of healthcare systems, and the application of seismic isolation

techniques [32]. Specific methodologies, such as hazard-based seismic design and probabilistic risk assessment, have identified limitations in traditional seismic resilience approaches [33]. These studies reveal significant shortcomings in traditional seismic design methods [33], emphasize the essential role of community resilience in disaster risk management [25], highlight the critical need for robust healthcare systems to respond effectively after earthquakes [34], and discuss how seismic isolation can help create communities that are sustainably resilient to such disasters by reducing the vulnerability of critical infrastructure and maintaining essential services during seismic events [35]. Also, incorporating cultural sensitivity as a foundational aspect of community engagement [36] is essential for ensuring that resilience measures resonate with local populations. Recognizing and integrating cultural values into preparedness efforts helps build trust and fosters greater acceptance of recommended safety practices by tailoring response and preparedness strategies that align with local beliefs and customs, thus enhancing community buy-in [37].

Furthermore, studies on earthquake preparedness, particularly among residents in rural areas affected by events like the 2008 Wenchuan earthquake in China, have been extensive [38–40]. These studies have pinpointed key factors that influence how individuals prepare for such disasters, including access to independent information about earthquakes, understanding of seismic risks, and confidence in personal and community response capabilities. Data from these studies underscore the role of education and prior experience in shaping individuals' responses to disaster scenarios, illustrating how knowledge can mitigate fear and facilitate action [4,9,12,35,40–51]. Findings indicate that individuals who possess a comprehensive understanding of disaster management are more likely to act decisively, such as evacuating promptly or quickly resuming their usual activities post-disaster, compared to those with limited knowledge, who may delay action while waiting for further instructions [4,9,12,35,40–53].

Effective strategies for local governance to increase seismic resilience are an essential part of preparing urban and regional communities to be able to cope with the impacts of earthquakes and recover [54–56]. These methods are very important for earthquake-vulnerable areas because they help in reducing earthquake damage and promote sustainability. By implementing building codes that mandate seismic retrofitting and resilience measures, these governance frameworks ensure that communities are protected in the long term [57]. At the core of these strategies are preventive actions that oblige urban legislation for buildings and infrastructure to be armed or adapted so as not to collapse during seismic shocks [55]. Such actions not only save the

immediate environment but also help the community become more resilient in the long haul [58]. Studies have shown that local governance frameworks, when incorporating resilience metrics, zoning regulations, and compliance enforcement, can significantly reduce earthquake damage [59,60]. The effectiveness of local governance in fostering seismic resilience can vary greatly depending on regional planning [61]. Authorities may develop diverse, customized plans that cater to their specific environmental and seismic challenges, underscoring the importance of personalized resilience strategies [62].

At the community and structural level, incorporating resilience goals into the seismic design of buildings and urban planning significantly enhances the speed of recovery after earthquakes [63]. This approach combines community-centric resilience strategies with precise engineering practices to better protect and serve the population during seismic events [64]. Furthermore, developing evaluation models to assess seismic resilience is crucial. These models take into account various important factors, including recovery speed, the effectiveness of disaster relief efforts, and the demographic and economic traits of the area, aiding in the refinement of emergency plans [65]. Incorporating systems dynamics within governance frameworks can enhance the understanding and development of seismic resilience. This technique is particularly useful in modern contexts like Society 5.0, where new technologies and societal needs are merged to optimize disaster management [66]. In places like Tabriz City or regions previously impacted by disasters such as the Gorkha Earthquake, governance strategies are specifically tailored to address the unique environmental and societal challenges, ensuring effective and customized resilience measures [67].

Recent studies have highlighted the significance of interdisciplinary approaches in enhancing earthquake resilience, particularly by combining engineering practices with social sciences to improve community preparedness and structural resilience [1,68]. This interdisciplinary method emphasizes the role of social factors, such as trust in local institutions and community engagement, in reinforcing physical infrastructure efforts. For instance, research demonstrates that communities with stronger social networks and trust in disaster response agencies are more likely to adopt and maintain seismic retrofitting and emergency planning measures [69]. Similarly, some research studies suggest that involving residents in the decision-making process related to building codes and disaster readiness can foster higher compliance rates and improve the overall impact of resilience policies [70].

2 Methods

The primary objectives of this study are to assess the current state of seismic resilience, identify critical gaps in local preparedness, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing response mechanisms. In this research, we carried out eight semi-structured interviews with individuals from regions highly prone to seismic activities, particularly those who have experienced notable earthquake impacts. Understanding Montenegro's tectonic features is essential for pinpointing areas most susceptible to seismic hazards, which in turn strengthens resilience and disaster preparedness strategies. By using geological data to identify high-risk zones, this research aids in developing targeted resilience measures that allow communities to better anticipate and reduce the impacts of earthquakes.

To acquire a more thorough and nuanced understanding, essential for effectively processing the data gathered from the survey on citizens' resilience to earthquake-induced disasters, it is nearly impossible to justify without conducting adequately structured interviews. These interviews serve as indispensable tools in complementing the questionnaire data, allowing for a more comprehensive examination of citizens' perspectives on the resilience of local communities in responding to earthquakes.

For this specific purpose, eight interviews were conducted with citizens hailing from the localities most vulnerable to seismic activity and those that have borne the brunt of earthquake consequences. The interviews engaged collaborators from Nikšić, Podgorica, Bar, Kotor, Cetinje, Budva, Herceg Novi, and Berane. Each collaborator was presented with an identical set of questions, following which the conversation was guided by participants' inclinations, motivations, level of engagement, and sincerity.

Employing a semi-structured approach, these interviews were designed around a conversation guide that mirrored the conceptual framework of the questionnaire (Figure 1):

- (1) How would you define citizen resilience in responding to disasters, particularly those triggered by earthquakes? What components do you believe it should encompass?
- (2) What is your overall perspective on the level of citizen resilience in addressing earthquakes as disasters? Please provide a detailed explanation of your viewpoint.
- (3) Regarding citizens' resilience in the face of earthquake disasters, what is your general assessment of their knowledge about earthquakes? Kindly elaborate on your opinion.

Figure 1: Mindmap of questions from semi-structured interviews on citizen resilience in earthquake disasters in Montenegro.

- (4) Concerning citizens' preparedness for earthquake disasters, what is your general assessment regarding their stockpiling of food and water supplies? Please elaborate on your viewpoint.
- (5) Regarding citizens' readiness for earthquake disasters, particularly at the household level, what is your general perspective on the effectiveness of oral or written disaster preparedness plans? Please provide a detailed explanation.
- (6) In terms of citizens' readiness for earthquake disasters, what is your general perspective on their engagement in activities such as evacuation drills? Please elaborate on your viewpoint.
- (7) How do you evaluate and what factors, in your opinion, influence citizens' motivation to undertake specific resilience measures in response to earthquake disasters? Kindly provide a detailed explanation.
- (8) What, in your opinion, are the primary obstacles preventing citizens from implementing certain resilience measures in response to earthquake disasters? Please elaborate on your viewpoint.
- (9) How would you assess the resilience of local self-governments in responding to earthquake disasters? Kindly provide a detailed explanation of your opinion.
- (10) In your view, what strategies could be implemented to enhance citizens' resilience in responding to earthquakes as disasters, particularly in terms of knowledge, preparedness supplies, preventive measures, and possession of plans? Please provide a detailed explanation.
- (11) Based on your observations, what is the resilience level of households in Montenegro in responding to earthquake disasters? Please provide a detailed explanation.
- (12) What specific actions do you believe local self-governments should take to elevate citizens' resilience levels in responding to earthquakes? Please elaborate on your opinion.

Figure 3: Study area: (a) location of Montenegro; maps of seismic re-ionization of Montenegro territory within the return periods of 200 years (b) and the return period of 500 years (c). Based on the Institute of Hydrometeorology and Seismology of Montenegro.

systems that have been meticulously catalogued during the pursuit of oil exploration. These systems reveal a landscape teeming with overturned and reverse-overturned structures, bordered to the northeast by the formidable Budva-Cukalj zone. Surface features such as Volujica-Šasko Lake, Možura-Briska Mountain, and Bijela Mountain stand as testaments to the geological diversity, with Cretaceous carbonates and Eocene flysch sediments adorning their cores [71,72].

Meanwhile, the Budva-Cukalj zone traces a sinuous path along Montenegro's coastal fringes, spanning from Sutomore in the northwest to the undulating slopes of Orjen, Lovćen, Sutorina, and Rumija, before traversing through Albania to Greece. Initially characterized by a rift structure, spanning a width of 40–100 km, this zone underwent a metamorphosis during the Alpine orogenesis, converging into a system of overturned isoclines, fractured and partitioned by thrusts. This region emerges as one of Montenegro's most dynamically altered terrains, a testament to the tumultuous forces shaping its geological identity.

Venturing further into Montenegro's heartland unveils the High Karst, a realm encompassing the central expanse and coastal fringes. From Rumija, Lovćen, and Orjen in the southwest to Volujak, Plužine, Durmitor, Šemolj, Kolašin, Tresnjevik, and Komovi in the northwest, this domain stands as a testament to nature's architectural prowess. Comprising the Old Montenegrin and Kučka nappe, separated by the synclinorium of Zeta, this region's geological narrative is one of juxtaposition. The Old Montenegrin unit, with its intricate anticlinorium, cascades into a mosaic of anticlinal-synclinal sets, while the Kučka unit, adorned with carbonate rocks and Durmitor flysch sediments, paints a picture of geological splendour. Finally, the Durmitor tectonic unit,

nestled in Montenegro's northeastern reaches, represents a bastion of geological intrigue. Separated from its predecessors by reverse dislocations along the Dinarides, this unit is a treasure trove of thrusts, emblematic of the region's geological dynamism [71,72].

Geological hazards that are caused by the tectonic movements in the Earth's crust are called earthquakes or minor quakes. The territory of Montenegro is an area with high seismic risk, with frequent small to moderate-sized earthquakes, and occasionally very strong, devastating earthquakes (Figure 3b and c). Hence, as the particularly active seismic area, the following zones should be emphasized: seismologic zones around Ulcinj and Bar, Budva and Brajići, Boka Kotorska but also immediate surroundings of Berane, the entire region of the Skadar Lake, Maganik, etc. The maps of seismic re-ionization of Montenegro reflect possible seismic intensity degrees divide several zones of different seismic hazards: The southern, coastal region with Ulcinj, Skadar, Budva, and Boka Kotorska zones with the possible maximum intensity (in the middle ground) of nine degrees of the Mercalli (MSC) scale, Podgorica–Danilovgrad zone with the expected maximum intensity of eight degrees of MSC scale, the central part of Montenegro with the northern region including Nikšić, Žabljak, and Pljevlja with the possible maximum intensity of seven degrees of the MSC scale, and an isolated seismologic Berane zone that may generate earthquakes with a maximum intensity of eight degrees on the MSC scale (Figure 3b and c). Montenegro's tectonic activity, driven by the convergence of major tectonic plates, results in significant seismic potential across the region. This geological dynamic underpins the frequency and intensity of earthquakes, setting the stage for

understanding how specific geological structures contribute to the area's seismic risk.

Countless seismic events have shaken the shores of Montenegro, yet many have slipped by unnoticed. Pliny, in the ancient corridors of the first century, penned an account of a cataclysmic earthquake that laid waste to Epidaurum, known today as Cavtat. The annals of history recall Duklja's torment in 518 AD when the earth convulsed beneath its feet. Kotor, in the cruel dance of fate, witnessed ruin twice over, first in 1520 and then in 1559, both times under the relentless grip of seismic fury. Legend speaks of the harrowing day of June 13, 1563, when every corner of Boka was razed to the ground by an earthquake of indeterminate magnitude, yet monstrous in its wrath. Echoes of a similar tremor resonated through Boka in 1608. The year 1667 etched its mark in blood and rubble, as Kotor, Perast, Risan, Herceg Novi, Budva, Bar, and Ulcinj succumbed to destruction. The annals bear witness to temblors of magnitude surpassing the IX degree on the Mercalli scale, their fury unleashed upon the Montenegrin coast in 1780 and 1830, and again in 1905, 1926, and 1927. These seismic convulsions not only assailed the coastline but also reverberated through the valleys of Podgorica-Skadar and Berane (Radojičić, 2008), including the devastating quake of 1979.

The earnest pursuit of seismic understanding in Montenegro traces its origins to the nineteenth century, when scholars meticulously chronicled the tremors that scarred their land, primarily through statistical analysis. The dawn of the twentieth century heralded a new era as seismic endeavours in Serbia began to dissect macroseismic data across the Balkans, Montenegro included. The illustrious work of Jelenko Mihajlović stands as a testament to this scholarly pursuit. The genesis of Montenegro's seismic instrumentation unfolded in March 1960, with the establishment of the Seismological Observatory in Titograd, now enshrined as Podgorica. This institution, born in the crucible of necessity, evolved into the Republic Seismological Institute following the tumult of April 15, 1979 (Ivanović, 1991). Despite these

strides, substantive inquiry into Montenegro's seismic landscape remained a rarity until the tragic cataclysm of April 15, 1979.

2.2 Socio-economic and demographic characteristics of respondents

The sample analysed in our study achieved 50% of the subjects being men and 50% women. This gives an idea of different life stages possibly affecting the disaster response as they reach from young adults at 22 to older adults at 60. The educational level of the participants ranges from secondary professional training to a PhD, which makes it possible to investigate whether disaster preparedness and resilience are influenced by high or low levels of education. The sample is mixed in terms of employment status as shown in Table 1, with the largest % being fully employed (25%), followed by retired (25%) both percentages are equivalent. This variation speaks to some diversity in economic circumstances and that could have relevance for a variety of preparations against emergencies. Only seven of the sampled women were married including only two who had been married for a long time, with 40% being single and never married, another third divorced after marriage failure when progeny or paternity claims surfaced then sending them back to their "absent husbands," while the final fourth of interviewed people admitted that they had contemplated suicide following the financial disaster which malediction apparently afflicted true partners in this case as well – even though these lucky couples leveraged multiple tenders! The participants had a monthly income between 300€ and 1,150€; therefore, they were in distinct financial situations that may affect the feasibility of investing in disaster prevention measures. The sample was independently selected school should understand that the geographical distribution of the limited urban and rural schools

Table 1: Demographic and socioeconomic profiles of interviewees in Montenegro

ID	Gender	Age	Education	Income	Interview location	Interview duration (min)	Employment status	Marital status
1	Male	58	Secondary professional	450€	Nikšić	37	Employed	Married
2	Male	35	Graduate lawyer	1,150€	Podgorica	44	Employed	Single
3	Female	26	Master's in geography	800€	Bar	65	Employed	Married
4	Female	28	Student/seasonal worker	500€	Budva	52	Part-time	Single
5	Male	45	PhD	950€	Cetinje	48	Self-employed	Married
6	Female	30	Bachelor's in economics	700€	Kotor	55	Unemployed	Divorced
7	Male	22	College student	300€	Herceg Novi	40	Student	Single
8	Female	60	Retired teacher	600€	Tivat	50	Retired	Widow

Table 2: Defining citizen resilience in response to earthquake-induced disasters

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	Citizen resilience to earthquakes encompasses preparedness and awareness of proper response to disasters. Achieving such resilience hinges crucially on possessing knowledge of protective measures and proper conduct during earthquakes. Education and practical training represent essential steps towards bolstering citizens' capacity for independent response and minimizing the adverse consequences of such natural events	Education, preparedness, training	62.5
2	Citizen resilience entails the undertaking of all available measures and activities to mitigate the consequences of earthquakes as disasters. It implies coordination between state and local authorities, citizens, and institutions most prepared and equipped to respond in given situations. As earthquakes entail both material and immaterial losses, it is imperative to initiate actions aimed at increasing the resilience of local communities in earthquake-prone areas promptly and seriously. Particularly in high-risk zones, it is necessary to introduce and prepare the population through programs and plans for responding to such situations	Coordination, governance, preparedness	50
3	Citizen resilience in responding to disasters, especially earthquakes, represents the ability of all organs and institutions in local self-governance to react adequately to mitigate the consequences that earthquakes may cause. To this end, it is essential to involve all physically capable citizens who, through specific types of education and training, would be ready to respond in the event of an earthquake.	Local governance, education, resilience	37.5
4	Resilience encompasses all preventive actions that society and citizens undertake to secure safer environments in the event of disasters, such as earthquakes. These actions may involve organizing citizens to familiarize them with the consequences of earthquakes and preparing them to act appropriately in such emergencies, thereby reducing the negative consequences of this phenomenon. In essence, it is about creating a community capable of responding adequately to earthquakes as disasters	Preventive measures, organization, preparedness	75
5	Citizen resilience in responding to disasters caused by earthquakes involves adequate response in the event of earthquakes. This can be achieved if we have capable individuals who know how to react in such situations, as well as the knowledge and ability of citizens to react in such situations	Preparedness, resilience, knowledge	52.5
6	Citizen resilience in responding to disasters caused by earthquakes is reflected in the ability, readiness, knowledge, will, and desire of citizens to respond in the event of earthquakes	Capacity, knowledge, readiness	37.5
7	Resilience represents the society's strength to cope with disasters, implying general preparedness and readiness for an adequate response from all institutions and citizens in given situations. Institutions are expected to react professionally, while citizens are expected to show solidarity	Solidarity, preparedness, institutions	50
8	Citizen resilience could be seen as the organized readiness of society to respond adequately to disasters caused by earthquakes. It involves implementing knowledge, preparation, and training aimed at achieving better preparedness for responding in the event of earthquakes	Organized readiness, training, preparation	61

Table 3: Assessment of citizen resilience in coping with earthquake disasters

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	Low earthquake preparedness in society is highlighted by inadequate coverage of the topic in the media and educational system. Limited educational programs on television and the absence of training in schools, particularly for children, result in a lack of knowledge and skills necessary for appropriate responses. Communication with citizens is minimal, falling short of addressing their needs and the associated hazards. Consequently, citizens, lacking education and proper resources, are left to rely on instinctive reactions during earthquakes	Media coverage, educational gaps, communication	45
2	Except for the aftermath of the significant earthquake in 1979, little attention has been devoted to fostering a resilient society against earthquakes. Most citizens remain uneducated and uninformed about the dangers posed by these natural events, posing a significant challenge when attempting to implement initiatives to acquaint citizens with these hazards and their repercussions	Historical awareness, citizen education, hazard awareness	40
3	Considering earthquakes demand swift responses, citizens should at least be familiar with proper reaction methods. Unfortunately, it appears that this awareness remains at a very low level, limited to a few basic directives on actions and responses, making it challenging to definitively assess the level of resilience. However, this issue certainly warrants increased attention	Swift response, low awareness, basic directives	50
4	Regrettably, it seems we have yet to establish a society resilient enough to withstand such occurrences. In the face of disasters, we mostly rely on regional assistance, indicating our lack of self-reliance and readiness to tackle such difficulties, including those caused by earthquakes. Consequently, it is evident that as a society, our level of resilience in citizen response to earthquakes and overall preparedness for disasters caused by earthquakes is not commendable	Self-reliance, regional assistance, low preparedness	30
5	Citizens are not adequately informed about how to respond in the event of disasters caused by earthquakes. This is largely due to insufficient dissemination of information through media channels, brochures, flyers, social networks, etc. Consequently, it can be concluded that as a society, we lack the necessary awareness and education on how to react in the event of earthquakes, resulting in a low level of citizen resilience in responding to disasters caused by earthquakes	Information dissemination, awareness, low resilience	55
6	In my view, the level of resilience is satisfactory. While there are services responsible for earthquake response, enhancing resilience would involve better informing citizens about their roles and contributions during earthquakes	Citizen roles, satisfactory resilience, improvement	25
7	In my opinion, resilience is not at a high level. Institutions compete for political gains, while citizens increasingly distance themselves from one another, painting a negative picture. In a time where empathy and solidarity are dwindling, there is a lack of inclination to aid or even listen to others in need	Institutional competition, social disconnect, low empathy	35
8	Unfortunately, the level of resilience is not commendable. This conclusion is drawn from observations in our city and country. There is a noticeable absence of efforts to build a more resilient society against earthquakes, indicating a lack of preparation and implementation of measures to increase resilience	Absence of resilience building, preparation, implementation	20

Table 4: Primary obstacles to implementing resilience measures in response to earthquake

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	The greatest barrier is the lack of personnel and staff to conduct oral and practical education sessions. Additionally, limited resources and citizens' lack of desire to learn more about the consequences of earthquakes pose significant challenges	Lack of personnel, limited resources, disinterest	30
2	The main barriers include the lack of information, namely, ignorance about the dangers earthquakes pose and how to react in such situations. Ignorance takes precedence. Alongside this, we can cite societal indifference, at both the individual and governmental levels, towards improving the resilience of local communities. The absence of adequate oversight in construction projects, as evidenced by the example of Turkey, where corruption and incompetent or irresponsible inspections by professionals are the primary barriers. Citizens' disinterest in education, as well as the apathy of institutions and authorities responsible for implementing certain activities, are also highlighted as barriers	Ignorance, societal indifference, corruption	40
3	In my opinion, the main barrier is the lack of knowledge about resilience measures, coupled with a lack of desire and willingness to educate ourselves and prepare for such situations. We could say its individual negligence towards the community, and ultimately, towards oneself and one's loved ones, stemming from the fact that we are unaware and uninformed about the dangers posed by this natural disaster. Thus, ignorance is the fundamental barrier to taking resilience measures in response to earthquakes.	Lack of knowledge, negligence, unawareness	35
4	Barriers can be financial resources allocated for financing educational workshops, conducting demonstrative exercises, paying instructors, providing spaces for education, etc. Additionally, a lack of personnel and citizens' disinterest in taking resilience measures against earthquake-related disasters can be barriers	Financial constraints, lack of personnel, disinterest	25
5	Misunderstanding and denial of the real danger posed by earthquakes, caused by general ignorance and uninformedness among citizens about the potential consequences of earthquakes, also contribute. Negligence, lack of time, prioritizing other activities and priorities are factors as well	Ignorance, misunderstanding, competing priorities	20
6	The primary barrier is negligence, both on an individual and societal level. However, in my view, society bears greater responsibility because caring for citizens is the state's problem, just as caring for household members is an individual's concern	Negligence, societal responsibility, state obligation	15
7	The very lack of awareness and understanding that earthquakes can strike at any moment, endangering us, presents a barrier in terms of disinterest in taking certain measures to create a more resilient society	Lack of awareness, disinterest, resilience measures	10
8	The underlying issue lies in the fact that earthquakes are a phenomenon that can occur at any moment, and our vulnerability to them serves as a barrier to taking proactive measures. Many individuals fail to recognize the imminent threat, assuming it would not affect them directly. However, this complacency is dangerous, as it prevents the implementation of necessary precautions. In addition, the complexity of earthquake preparedness, coupled with the fast-paced nature of modern life, further contributes to this barrier. People are often overwhelmed with daily responsibilities and fail to prioritize disaster preparedness. Consequently, raising awareness about the real and immediate threat of earthquakes and emphasizing the importance of preparedness measures is crucial in overcoming this barrier	Vulnerability, complacency, preparedness complexity	5

Table 5: Assessment of local self-governments' resilience in responding to earthquake disasters

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	Once again, we encounter a personnel problem if there are not individuals available to conduct education. On the other hand, political entities predominantly focus on social and political issues, relegating others to the side lines, if mentioned at all. While institutions like the Civil Protection Service exist, I believe their capacity is insufficient to address the consequences of earthquakes	Personnel shortage, political focus, insufficient capacity	30
2	In my view, there is a certain level of preparedness, but it remains minimal. There is likely adequate documentation for mitigating earthquake consequences, but it's uncertain whether there's a specific document addressing earthquake resilience	Minimal preparedness, documentation gaps, earthquake resilience	25
3	I lack data and information about the activities of local authorities aimed at improving and strengthening resilience in the event of disasters caused by earthquakes. As a resident of this city, I can subjectively state that I am not aware of any activities undertaken by competent authorities to enhance resilience in the face of earthquakes, despite our city being in a highly seismic area, posing significant risks in the event of an earthquake	Lack of data, local authority inactivity, high seismic risk	20
4	It is difficult for me to express an opinion on this matter due to a lack of information. However, I believe and hope that we are somewhat prepared, considering the consequences left by the earthquake 45 years ago. So I hope we have learned some lessons from that situation. On the other hand, as a resident of this city, I have witnessed construction projects that I believe are unsuitable for this area, but I hope that expertise prevails	Lack of information, hope from past lessons, construction concerns	15
5	Considering that there has not been a major earthquake in Herceg Novi recently, I am not entirely sure if local authorities have developed a detailed disaster response plan for earthquakes	Uncertain plans, absence of major earthquakes, local preparedness	10
6	If we are discussing the problems ordinary citizens may face due to these events, which result from ignorance, I would say there is a significant problem with the actions of local and state institutions. On the other hand, I cannot speak about the condition, knowledge, and effectiveness of services trained to act in the event of earthquakes because I am not informed	Ignorance, institutional inaction, limited service knowledge	5
7	As I mentioned earlier, local governments, as well as state institutions at higher levels, do not pay enough attention and importance to this issue. I think they rely more on assistance from the region and Europe because they are aware that their level of readiness is very low. The question arises, what happens until that help arrives? I believe we are left on our own until then, with a small and insufficient number of experts who know how to handle these situations	Low governmental focus, reliance on external aid, expert shortage	35
8	Like citizens, I believe local governments are disinterested in this matter. The fact that an earthquake will occur is denied, and it is not given importance, while some other matters are considered more urgent, resulting in a passive society regarding this issue	Local government disinterest, denial of risk, passive society	40

negligence (by individual and collective citizens), and disinterest. These are aspects of education and awareness that have had too little particular salience or visibility in national policy discussions about resilience. From the analysis, it is

clear that the challenges of implementing individual strategies for seismic resilience are numerous and intertwined, necessitating a comprehensive strategy to combat this issue (Table 4 and Figure 6).

Table 6: Assessment of citizens' knowledge about earthquakes and resilience

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	In my assessment, citizens' understanding of disasters stemming from earthquakes remains at a distressingly low level. As I previously discussed, the root of this issue lies primarily in the inadequacies of formal education, particularly within schools where earthquake preparedness should be a mandatory component. Additionally, supplementary initiatives such as workshops, training sessions, and informative broadcasts are crucial to bolstering public knowledge. However, even when such efforts are undertaken, there persists a significant gap in informing citizens about these activities, presenting a challenge comparable to the lack of their execution	Low awareness, education gaps, public knowledge	35
2	Building upon my earlier response, I emphasized the insufficiency in disseminating information and the sluggish implementation of educational endeavours aimed at enhancing public awareness. Moreover, there exists a scarcity of scientific and educational programs targeting older demographics, utilizing social media platforms to educate the younger generation, and incorporating earthquake-related curricula into schools	Information dissemination, social media, curriculum integration	30
3	As I mentioned previously, I contend that substantive knowledge on this topic is scarce beyond a few instinctual responses based on hearsay, such as avoiding elevators or seeking shelter under door frames. I question whether the average citizen has been exposed to more comprehensive information through educational campaigns	Basic knowledge, instinctual responses, limited campaign exposure	45
4	This issue transcends our society; many countries, regardless of their level of development, grapple with similar hurdles. The increasingly routinized lifestyles and dwindling interpersonal interactions in both developed and developing nations contribute to a decline in empathy and willingness to assist others in times of need. Daily routines have alienated us from matters deemed "secondary," neglecting vital aspects of personal and communal significance. Consequently, citizens lack knowledge due to detachment and apathy towards objectively crucial matters, which is not unique to our context. The scarcity of time in today's fast-paced world exacerbates this problem, resulting in the neglect of critical issues like earthquake preparedness	Global issue, decline in empathy, routine alienation	40
5	As previously stated, I believe citizens possess only a rudimentary understanding of earthquakes, capable of explaining the basic concept and potential consequences in broad strokes. However, I doubt many individuals, especially those outside professional circles, possess a deeper comprehension of earthquake-related subjects	Rudimentary understanding, lack of depth, professional knowledge	30
6	In my view, citizens' capacity to respond to earthquakes, as it pertains to their understanding of earthquakes, is notably deficient. This conclusion stems from the widespread lack of education about earthquake-related disasters, compounded by an inadequate grasp of appropriate responses in earthquake scenarios. The dearth of effective communication channels for educating citizens about their preparedness, particularly regarding earthquake awareness, exacerbates this situation	Deficient response capacity, lack of communication channels, preparedness awareness	50

(Continued)

Table 7: Resilience level of households in Montenegro in responding to earthquake disasters

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	I think that in most cases, resilience is weak. Many buildings are being constructed or already built outside of the regulations set for construction works. Old structures were built according to earlier standards, and we still witness unplanned construction today. Household members are not familiar with basic reactions in the event of such disasters, both older and newer buildings lack adequate equipment for protection	Weak resilience, non-compliant construction, lack of equipment	40
2	My opinion is that citizens do not give significant importance to the dangers of earthquakes. Mild tremors are common here, but stronger ones have not occurred recently, so citizens have not developed a fear of this natural phenomenon. Mostly, we hear about destructive earthquakes happening in distant places that cannot threaten us, thus unfortunately underestimating the fact that extremely strong tremors have occurred here and there is a real danger of them recurring	Low awareness, underestimated risk, lack of fear	35
3	I believe that the resilience of households in Montenegro regarding earthquake response is at an undesirable level. Inadequate education, lack of emphasis on the potential consequences of earthquakes in our region, especially in coastal areas and central parts, contribute to this. It all comes down to fear when tremors occur, seeking information on where it happened, and that is where all curiosity about that event ends. Unfortunately, the need for information that could be useful is either unavailable or there is no citizen interest in getting educated	Undesirable resilience, inadequate education, information gap	30
4	I think it is not at a high level, precisely because there are no educational programs for citizens, thus depriving them of certain information and knowledge on how to react in the event of an earthquake	Absence of educational programs, knowledge deficit, reaction preparedness	25
5	My opinion is that household resilience in the event of an earthquake boils down to reflexive action. In the event of an earthquake, it is important to find a safe place, which usually involves an evacuation plan. What follows after that is a matter of "higher force"	Reflexive action, evacuation planning, dependence on higher forces	20
6	In my opinion, it is very poor. Ignorance is the biggest problem, but citizens do not prioritize that knowledge because they are not aware of the danger until they find themselves in that situation	Poor knowledge, ignorance, lack of awareness	15
7	Poor! I think there are no households in Montenegro where these matters are discussed or contemplated. If mentioned somewhere, it is only briefly. There is no drive to discuss it, except in the immediate aftermath of an earthquake, and even then, the conversation about how to react is lacking, merely commenting on the situation depicted in the media	Lack of discussion, media depiction, reactive conversations	10
8	At a low level again. The lack of interest and the lack of built awareness that danger lurks and can happen at any moment. Citizens are relaxed about this matter and do not take any action because they do not have a sense of negative fear but are rather indifferent to it	Low interest, indifference, lack of fear	5

Table 9: Assessment of the effectiveness of oral and written disaster preparedness plans among citizens for earthquake readiness, particularly at the household level

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	My opinion is that citizens' resilience in responding to disasters caused by earthquakes in terms of verbal/written protection and rescue plans is very poor. Once again, we have the same problems as in previous situations: lack of awareness, and unawareness of the consequences earthquakes bring. The last significant earthquake in our area occurred in 1979, and at that time, part of the population was educated. However, the majority of citizens living in Montenegro today are not aware of the danger posed by earthquakes. Consequently, households do not develop sufficiently good communication when it comes to these dangers. The reason for this is a sense of comfort and security that such a catastrophe will not happen, which is again a consequence of lack of information and ignorance	Poor resilience, lack of awareness, communication gap	35
2	If there are a certain number, I doubt even more, printed brochures in the form of protection and rescue plans, I believe even less that citizens have preserved them, let alone put them in a visible place and pay attention to them. As for verbal plans, considering that there have been strong earthquakes in the immediate vicinity recently, the knowledge they have acquired is perhaps from reporting from the scene or TV programs on this topic	Printed brochures, verbal plans, media awareness	30
3	As a person living in this country, I am aware that there is a protection and rescue plan issued by the Government of Montenegro, but I have not noticed any concrete and practical steps. So, we possess a document, but besides that document, available on the website of the Government of Montenegro, I do not see concrete actions for that document to reach a larger number of citizens	Government plan, limited public reach, lack of action	25
4	I think we have insufficient information regarding these issues. I assume that we have appropriate documents, and elaborates, but citizens themselves are deprived of that information because they mostly consider it insignificant. This is a natural phenomenon that may or may not happen soon, so it is set aside, which is a big problem because an earthquake can happen any minute, and we as citizens are neither aware of that nor do we find it important because we believe it will not happen. So, I think it is a big problem that written protection plans are not attractive enough for citizens, while verbal ones are very few, or they do not exist at all	Insufficient information, citizen detachment, perceived insignificance	40
5	I think it boils down to some informal communication; if one hears that a devastating earthquake has occurred somewhere in the world, it might be discussed within the family circle. But a specific conversation aimed at education, conveying, and sharing knowledge, I think, is not present	Informal communication, lack of educational conversations	20
6	We live alienated lives. Communication, even with relatives, is reduced to a minimum, so I do not believe that discussions on these topics take place, while written plans are completely excluded	Alienation, minimal communication, absence of plans	15
7	This is related to the question of education. Considering that there is no awareness, or knowledge of how to react, I think protection plans do not exist in households either. I believe they would only have instinctive reactions	Education deficit, instinctive reactions, household plans	10
8	I think there are no plans at the household level. I myself have not made a plan, neither written nor verbal, and I believe the	No household plans, limited awareness, evacuation posters	5

(Continued)

Table 10: Evaluation of citizens' stockpiling of food and water supplies for earthquake preparedness

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	If we consider the opportunity we had to witness the extent of citizens' stockpiles during the coronavirus pandemic, we can conclude that preparations were very poor. The difference is that citizens had time to react and replenish their supplies in the first scenario, whereas in the case of stronger earthquakes, this is often impossible due to the extensive damage. Once again, I would like to refer to state and local institutions, which could have learned from the pandemic example to identify issues that our society faces in similar situations	Stockpiles, pandemic comparison, institutional learning	45
2	I believe that possession of stockpiles in the form of food and water is at a very low level, often limited to basic daily necessities. Citizens do not prioritize the possibility of a stronger earthquake occurring, as they primarily focus on everyday matters, believing that such events either would not happen or would not affect them directly	Low stockpile levels, earthquake risk perception, daily priorities	40
3	I think that serious stockpiling efforts are not being made, especially in urban households where numerous supermarkets are readily available, and thoughts of disasters are almost non-existent. In rural households, I presume the situation is different, considering that agriculture is one of the main activities, leading to stockpiles of vegetables, homemade meat, and the like	Urban vs rural stockpiling, accessibility, disaster preparedness	35
4	As I mentioned before, we live fast-paced lives and do not have time for some basic things and activities. Yet, readily available items are easily accessible. People no longer buy large quantities of food but rather what is needed for, let's say, a week. Therefore, I believe that in a more serious sense, we cannot talk about stockpiles	Fast-paced lifestyle, short-term supplies, lack of stockpiles	30
5	I believe that the situation is alarming in this regard as well. I'm not sure if there is still time for food stockpiling, considering that freezers are almost nonexistent and canned food is no longer as attractive as it used to be. Therefore, I think that very few households make food reserves, especially out of fear of a natural disaster like an earthquake	Alarming situation, food preservation, natural disaster fear	25
6	The same goes for none! People live from hand to mouth, focusing on the present without considering stockpiles. Perhaps if someone has relatives in the countryside or prepares preserves for the winter, if we can classify that as stockpiling, besides that, it is hard to find anyone with ready supplies for a longer period	Living hand to mouth, lack of preparedness, limited stockpiles	20
7	The answer is the same as before. Citizens are not aware that we are in an earthquake-prone area, mainly because the last major earthquake with significant consequences happened almost half a century ago, so citizens became complacent regarding this issue. That's why serious food and water reserves are not being created, as we noticed even a couple of years ago during the pandemic when supermarkets were full of citizens and shelves were empty. Therefore, there were no reserves; people reacted in the given moment	Complacency, earthquake prone area, pandemic reflection	15
8	If we consider the opportunity we had to witness the extent of citizens' stockpiles during the coronavirus pandemic, we can conclude that preparations were very poor. The difference is that citizens had time to react and replenish their supplies in the first scenario, whereas in the case of stronger earthquakes, this is often impossible due to the extensive damage. Once again, I would like to refer to state and local institutions, which could have learned from the pandemic example to identify issues that our society faces in similar situations	Pandemic insight, institutional responsibility, poor preparations	10

Table 11: Evaluation of citizens' engagement in evacuation drills for earthquake preparedness

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	Once upon a time, there existed a service known as Civil Protection, which regularly conducted exercises to prepare citizens for potential dangers. Through these exercises, citizens were educated and equipped with the necessary skills to respond effectively in hazardous situations. Unfortunately, in today's context, similar governmental bodies or organizations are either non-existent or limited to rescue services and fire departments. Consequently, it appears that citizens are largely left to rely on their instincts and reflexes when faced with dangers such as earthquakes	Civil protection, historical context, citizen skills	40
2	In my opinion, there is a glaring lack of evacuation exercises being conducted by citizens from their homes in the event of earthquakes. I am almost certain that this practice is not commonplace in households across Montenegro	Lack of evacuation drills, household preparedness	35
3	Expanding on the previous point, while we may possess documents outlining emergency procedures, there seems to be a significant gap when it comes to actual implementation. There is a notable absence of training, educational initiatives, or efforts to raise awareness about the importance of knowing how to react in emergency situations. At least from my perspective, I have not encountered any such activities	Implementation gap, absence of training, awareness	30
4	To be frank, I am not aware of any ongoing exercises of this nature, but I strongly believe they should be taking place. If my information is incorrect, it is because I have not personally witnessed any exercises of this kind	Need for exercises, lack of visibility, citizen awareness	25
5	I am aware that in the past, during the time of the SFRY, there was an entity called Civil Protection tasked with responding to various hazardous situations. They underwent training and were knowledgeable about how to react in specific scenarios. Whether a similar organization still exists today is unknown to me, but I believe it would be incredibly beneficial if it did. I assume that the responsibilities of Civil Protection may now fall under the jurisdiction of the Protection and Rescue Service	Civil protection history, protection, and rescue service	20
6	In my humble opinion, based on my limited experience, information, and knowledge in this field, it appears that citizens are not actively engaged in such preparedness activities. I can only deduce that my lack of awareness regarding these matters may stem from a lack of commitment from relevant institutions and authorities to provide citizens with the necessary knowledge and skills	Institutional commitment, preparedness activities, citizen engagement	15
7	Furthermore, it seems that opportunities to participate in such exercises have significantly diminished over time. While we may have had access to exercises conducted by firefighters in the past, these events are now scarcely remembered. It is my firm belief that evacuation exercises should be implemented across all institutions where large numbers of people gather, including schools, government offices, hospitals, and more	Diminished opportunities, institutional exercises, public facilities	10
8	Considering the discontinuation of mandatory military service, civil protection, and similar bodies, it is evident that there is a gap in preparedness training for citizens	Military service discontinuation, preparedness gap, civil protection	5

Table 12: Strategies to enhance citizens' resilience in responding to earthquakes by local self-governments

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	I think that multi-faceted disinterest is the predominant problem. Neither citizens show interest in educating themselves, nor do local authorities conduct specific activities to implement this education. It is necessary to employ individuals, and involve volunteers, the Red Cross, and NGOs, all under the auspices of the service responsible for conducting these activities	Citizen disinterest, lack of activities, volunteer involvement	30
2	My opinion is that citizen awareness is low, except for potential individuals whose profession is closely related to these natural phenomena	Low awareness, professional knowledge, limited interest	25
3	My assessment is that citizen awareness is influenced by several factors. Education programs, if they exist and are implemented, would be followed by citizen interest in educating and informing themselves	Awareness factors, education programs, citizen interest	20
4	It depends on their interest, willingness, and desire to expand their knowledge. Besides, conditions and opportunities to acquire more detailed information and participate in potential training also influence this	Interest and willingness, knowledge expansion, training opportunities	15
5	I rate it relatively poorly, and the reason is again the lack or inadequate information. Therefore, the media should dedicate much more space to educational programs of that and similar content. Then, awareness through social networks has proven to be very effective in recent practice, but it is taken with a certain reserve, considering that they often contain inaccuracies or disinformation	Poor information, media involvement, social media awareness	10
6	I think that the quantity of information on one side and citizens' interest in the same information on the other side have the most significant influence	Information quantity, citizen interest, knowledge gap	5
7	It depends on the state's interest in providing information to citizens. I mean educational institutions and the media, which are in the most favourable position to inform citizens about preventive measures for responding to a natural disaster caused by an earthquake	State responsibility, educational institutions, preventive measures	35
8	I believe that it is at a low level, which represents one of the burning problems concerning citizens' resilience. This is influenced by the insufficient dedication of state organs and citizens' disinterest in getting informed. Entertainment and politics take precedence, while issues of crucial importance receive minimal attention	Low awareness, state neglect, focus on entertainment	40

teaching earthquake courses at all school levels and using social networks as information channels, especially for younger population. The importance of distributing earthquake response information brochures is also highlighted.

Second is the need to stress more on food stockpile readiness, both at the state level, through local administrations, and by individuals. This also includes transparent information to citizens about the state of stockpiles and potential opportunities. Other suggestions include incorporating earthquake training and education into state exams, as well as holding regular school classes on the issue.

Third, workplaces should conduct regular exercises and drills to help citizens learn the appropriate earthquake response protocols. Suggestions for improvement include hiring permanent workers to oversee volunteers during drills and conducting community education on earthquake awareness. Throughout all proposed measures, the importance of raising awareness among citizens about the importance of prevention and earthquake preparedness is emphasized, as well as strengthening institutional capacities to deal with this risk. Overall, there is a consensus that only a combination of education, training, preventive measures,

Table 13: Evaluation of factors influencing citizens' motivation for resilience measures in earthquake disasters

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	In analysing citizens' motivation to undertake specific resilience measures in response to disasters caused by earthquakes, several key observations emerge. First, three respondents highlight the potential of introducing educational broadcasts as a means of motivating citizens. This suggests that disseminating information through such channels could serve as an effective method of educating the populace about potential dangers	Educational broadcasts, motivation, information dissemination	30
2	Second, four respondents emphasize the importance of educating younger members of society through workshops and educational films. This approach is deemed the most effective, long-lasting way to instil response capabilities	Youth education, workshops, long-lasting impact	35
3	Third, three respondents stress the importance of earthquake awareness as a motivation for taking resilience measures. Additionally, they propose organizing forums with rescuers to share experiences and advice with citizens	Awareness, forums with rescuers, experience sharing	25
4	Finally, two respondents underscore fear as the primary motivation for action but also highlight a lack of awareness about the dangers of earthquakes as a problem. Collectively, these results demonstrate that awareness of risks, education, and the opportunity to receive advice from experts are crucial motivators for citizens to take resilience measures in response to earthquakes	Fear, lack of awareness, risk education	20
5	In addition to the primary findings outlined earlier, it is noteworthy that some responses express a negative attitude towards the existing education and preparedness system for dealing with earthquakes. Respondents believe that current mechanisms are insufficiently effective and rely primarily on instinctive reactions in times of danger. This indicates a need for a shift towards education and raising awareness about earthquakes	Negative attitudes, instinctive reactions, system improvement	15
6	Furthermore, it is important to emphasize that citizens' motivation to undertake specific resilience measures may vary depending on various factors, including age, educational level, living conditions, and past experiences with disasters. Some respondents consider fear to be the most significant motivator, while others prioritize the protection and rescue of their loved ones. Additionally, there is evidence to suggest that citizens have differing perceptions of earthquake risks, highlighting the need for increased efforts in education and awareness on this critical issue	Varying motivations, demographic factors, risk perception	10
7	While education is generally considered the most effective motivator, other factors such as dedication, solidarity, and community responsibility can also contribute to enhancing citizens' resilience to earthquakes. By addressing these diverse motivators, efforts to increase earthquake resilience can be more comprehensive and effective, ultimately ensuring the safety and well-being of communities	Education, solidarity, community responsibility	5
8	Motivation among school-aged citizens can be achieved through workshops involving rescue services. Children are easily engaged; showing them educational films, introducing them to equipment, both professional and what can be found in our homes. This kind of education for the youngest members of society would be the most effective, long-lasting, and beneficial. Another advantage is that they would share their knowledge, passing on experiences from workshops to their parents and other household members. For adult citizens, I believe it is considerably more challenging to implement due to their daily activities and obligations. However, awareness of the dangers can indeed be a driving force for taking measures against this disaster	Youth engagement, workshops, household knowledge sharing	5

Table 14: Strategies to enhance citizens' resilience in responding to earthquake disasters

Participant ID	Key response segments	Key thematic terms	Frequency of theme (%)
1	The things I have been talking about in previous topics hold true here. Knowledge needs to be imparted from elementary schools to high schools and even at universities through specific courses. By using social media, we can easily provide information to young people about the consequences and dangers posed by earthquakes	School education, social media, youth awareness	40
2	As I mentioned before, education is the most important and effective way to improve citizens' resilience to earthquakes. This way, people gain knowledge on how to react in case of an earthquake, how to prepare themselves and their households, and by distributing brochures containing content related to disaster response due to earthquakes	Brochures, earthquake preparation, public knowledge	35
3	First, it is necessary to create certain commodity reserves in the form of basic food supplies at the national level, and then the same should be done individually by local governments and citizens in their households. How to improve this? First, state and local authorities should do this transparently by providing citizens with data on the status of stockpiles and how long they can temporally meet the population's needs. This way, attention is drawn to the fact that citizens, through certain programs and self-education, inform themselves about all the consequences. During certain state exams, one of the areas could be earthquake response, while in schools, this could be organized through regular classes. For other citizens, finding an adequate way to acquaint themselves with the dangers and, thus, build a more resilient society to these hazards through knowledge and skills	Stockpiles, transparency, knowledge programs	30
4	I believe that education and providing important information come first, followed by training and involving individuals in everyday activities related to the issue of citizens' resilience to earthquakes. This could involve employing permanent staff to accompany volunteers who would demonstrate specific exercises together and educate citizens through seminars on how to respond in case of earthquakes	Training, volunteer involvement, earthquake seminars	25
5	First, educating children in schools is essential, and then creating brochures and written materials as supplementary material for children and adults. Regarding creating food reserves, I think the country's financial situation plays a serious role, considering the citizens' standard of living. As for preventive measures, possessing plans, first, citizens need to be made aware of the importance, primarily, of building quality and other prevention measures, such as possessing tools, first aid equipment, fire extinguishers, etc.	School education, preventive measures, household preparedness	20
6	First, instructing citizens that this is a real danger threatening us and can happen at any moment, by reaching them with information about the importance of society's resilience in these situations. It is essential for all of us to be prepared and capable of reacting, helping, and influencing to minimize the consequences of earthquakes. All of this is achieved through adequate education provided to all citizens	Real danger awareness, community preparation, citizen skills	15
7	Education, training, and working on resilience strengthening. Education and training, as I said, from kindergartens to nursing homes. Institutions should engage in planning and developing strategies, training specialized personnel, creating teams to respond in case of a disaster, etc.	Comprehensive education, institutional training, response teams	10

(Continued)

Table 15: Seismic resilience recommendations with implementation, financial, and stakeholder considerations

Thematic heading	Recommendation	Specific actions	Implementation difficulty	Financial resources required	Stakeholders
Education and training	Develop comprehensive educational programs for all ages, embedding earthquake preparedness in school curricula, and leveraging social networks for information dissemination	Utilize detailed metrics to assess educational effectiveness across age groups	Moderate	Moderate	Educational institutions, local government, social media influencers
	Introduce earthquake-related topics in school curricula with regular evacuation drills and emergency response exercises to instill preparedness in students	Evaluate curriculum effectiveness and student preparedness regularly through drills	Moderate	Low	School boards, education departments, emergency response teams
	Provide earthquake safety training for households, offering practical opportunities to boost protection and preparedness	Encourage household-level resilience with distributed guidelines and tools for earthquake preparedness	Low	Low	Local councils, disaster management agencies, households
Collaboration and communication	Raise public awareness through targeted campaigns and hold mass evacuation drills to ensure citizens are familiar with evacuation procedures	Ensure targeted campaigns are tailored to specific community needs for accessibility	High	High	Local media, municipal authorities, community organizations
	Organize workshops and seminars to involve citizens in disaster preparedness and response activities	Offer participation incentives to increase community engagement	Moderate	Moderate	Community centres, NGOs, local educators
	Foster collaboration among residents, local institutions, and government bodies to align resilience efforts toward earthquake preparedness	Establish clear communication channels for coordination after earthquakes	Low	Low	Residents, local councils, disaster response teams
Policy and resource mobilization	Use public outreach and educational campaigns to raise awareness and establish formal communication channels for coordinated responses post-earthquake	Maintain consistent public outreach, using multiple platforms to enhance awareness	Moderate	Moderate	Public relations teams, local media, emergency responders
	Promote unity and collective action by fostering collaboration between local governments and community stakeholders	Include rural and urban stakeholders in collaboration efforts	Low	Low	Local governments, community leaders, residents
	Adopt policies to address information gaps, resource constraints, and political neglect with a focus on rebuilding and future earthquake response efforts	Set clear objectives for resource distribution and political accountability	High	High	Policy makers, disaster recovery agencies, resource management units
	Enhance education and awareness campaigns, and strengthen institutional capacity through civil society involvement to address coordination challenges	Utilize civil society networks for ongoing resilience efforts	High	Moderate	Educational NGOs, local institutions, civil society

(Continued)

Table 15: Continued

Thematic heading	Recommendation	Specific actions	Implementation difficulty	Financial resources required	Stakeholders
Evaluation and monitoring	Improve frameworks enabling local governments to execute earthquake resilience activities effectively	Define measurable goals for local resilience activities	Moderate	High	Municipal governments, resilience planners, local organizations
	Tailor solutions for local areas, quantify resources for at-risk regions, and address resilience disparities	Adapt solutions to unique community needs and vulnerabilities	High	High	Local authorities, resource management teams, affected communities
	Build cultural sensitivity into educational outreach to foster community ownership of preparedness messages rooted in local knowledge	Promote educational approaches that reflect cultural values for broader community impact	Moderate	Moderate	Cultural leaders, educational institutions, community members
	Include earthquake resilience considerations in planning of new developments to ensure they withstand natural hazards	Incorporate hazard resilience into building codes and standards	High	High	Construction companies, urban planners, regulatory bodies
	Integrate resilience into multilevel planning processes for sustainable, long-term solutions	Integrate resilience considerations into sustainable design for new developments	Moderate	High	Regional planning boards, sustainability councils, local government
	Convene multi-sector collaboration to integrate resilience into policy frameworks and mobilize financial resources for improvements	Encourage cross-sector cooperation for policy development and resource mobilization	High	High	Governmental bodies, private sector, funding agencies
	Develop monitoring and feedback mechanisms to assess the impact of resilience interventions and identify areas for improvement	Establish metrics to track and report on resilience outcomes	Moderate	Moderate	Data analysts, resilience coordinators, government officials
	Engage stakeholders in periodic evaluations and update strategies as part of an adaptive learning approach	Involve key stakeholders in evaluations to adapt and enhance strategies	Moderate	Moderate	Local governments, resilience task forces, community groups
	Use KPIs to assess resilience improvements and adjust programs as needed	Use KPIs for regular resilience measurement and reporting	High	High	Policy analysts, resilience evaluators, data scientists
	Conduct regular evaluations with specific metrics to track resilience progress and areas for refinement	Create clear evaluation protocols for continuous resilience program refinement	Moderate	High	Evaluation teams, government representatives, disaster management experts

have not directly faced the consequences of such events. For these reasons, they largely emphasize the necessity of improving resilience strategies and implementing preventive measures at both national and local levels. On the other hand, the obtained results also point to the low effectiveness of existing safety measures, as well as the need for additional research to examine all possible impacts of such events. The study's findings contribute to the broader theories of disaster risk management and resilience by emphasizing the importance of adaptable, community-based approaches to earthquake preparedness.

The study emphasizes the need for educational and preparedness programs tailored to address each community's unique vulnerabilities and strengths. By developing community-specific resilience measures, stakeholders can more effectively mitigate seismic risks in ways that are meaningful and practical for local residents. Increasing public awareness and strengthening local institutional readiness are crucial for enhancing resilience against seismic hazards. Public outreach initiatives, paired with improved response capabilities among local institutions, serve as foundational steps in building a robust disaster-preparedness framework. Concrete actions, such as regular community drills, targeted educational campaigns, and the integration of disaster preparedness content into school curricula, have been highlighted as actionable steps to increase public awareness and community resilience.

These findings contribute to the broader disaster risk management and resilience theories by offering insight into the real-world application of resilience strategies and by underscoring the necessity of adaptable, community-centred approaches. The analysis of all the results highlights the urgent need for Montenegrin society to strengthen its preparedness, and consequently its resilience, through educational programs and plans to mitigate the effects of future earthquakes. This requires strategic and operational commitment from society to devise, implement, and put into action all structural and non-structural measures that will enhance earthquake resilience. On the other hand, the study in many segments also emphasizes the importance of raising public awareness, as well as local and regional institutional readiness, to lift the low level of awareness about such disasters to a slightly higher level. The insights gained from this study can be effectively applied to other regions facing similar seismic risks. Policymakers and emergency planners in earthquake-prone areas can adapt these recommendations to their unique geographical and social landscapes.

Raising awareness would also enable a more rational perception of the risks associated with such disasters, which would lead to increased motivation for elevating the culture of resilience to a higher level. Certainly, a layered approach

at all societal levels, comprehensive institutional commitment, and involvement represent essential prerequisites for building such resilience. In addition, by promoting a proactive stance on resilience and strengthening education, infrastructure, and community engagement, Montenegro can improve its safety protocols and preparedness, fostering a more effective response to inevitable seismic activities. This study provides specific guidance for policymakers, particularly on implementing recommendations in ways that align with existing disaster preparedness frameworks. Policy adjustments to include resilience metrics, localized educational programs, and clear roles for community stakeholders are essential. Integrating these recommendations presents challenges, such as securing financial resources and public buy-in. However, solutions including public-private partnerships and engaging community leaders may help overcome these obstacles. Limitations, such as the focus on qualitative data and the sample size, suggest areas for further research. Future studies could include quantitative assessments and larger samples to broaden the findings and test their generalizability.

The high scientific and societal value of this research is reflected in its numerous implications for scientific and social development. The conducted research has generated a fundamental empirical database that can serve as a comparison of resilience levels between the region and the international community. The research marks the beginning of a pioneering endeavour for the further development of instruments for conducting quantitative and qualitative studies in the field of disaster risk management. In addition, the study contributes to the broader field of disaster (risk) management by providing a methodological framework that can be applied to assess and analyse community resilience when facing seismic challenges. It is also worth noting that the nuanced insights gained from the diverse experiences of Montenegrin municipalities enrich the academic discourse on preparedness and resilience to disasters, suggesting pathways for further research.

Contrary to the scientific implications, the societal implications are highly significant for policymakers and decision-makers at all levels, as they clearly highlight the weaknesses and challenges that must be overcome. The findings of the study can be considered when creating programs to improve the culture of resilience among the population. As such, they can be grounded and based on all identified shortcomings and clarifications derived from the comprehensive analysis of Montenegro's population resilience to earthquakes. This study highlights gaps, particularly in understanding how local community characteristics influence resilience. Further research is needed to examine the effectiveness of tailored education programs

and preparedness drills, and how these interventions impact overall disaster resilience at the community level. Specific areas for future investigation include the long-term effects of educational outreach programs, the role of community leaders in resilience-building, and the effectiveness of policy interventions in fostering a culture of preparedness. Such research could deepen understanding of the mechanisms that contribute to sustainable resilience. The variability in preparedness across different localities suggests that response strategies must be flexible and adapted to local needs. This study illustrates that a one-size-fits-all approach may not be effective; instead, response plans should reflect community-specific factors to optimize resilience and reduce risks.

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